

More on the civic countermarks of second-century Asia Minor

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In 2018 I assembled the evidence then known to me for a varied phenomenon of countermarking on the silver tetradrachm coinage of the second century BC. In this note I provide, first, an update to the catalogue I offered then, consisting both of some new specimens as well as seven new countermarks (5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 14.1, 15.1, 22.1, 26). I then discuss the attributions of these countermarks, together with the ramifications of this new evidence for the dating of these countermarking episodes. As in my original study, I divide the countermarks chronologically into three broad groups: early (c. 180-170 BC); middle (c. 170-150 BC) and late (post 150 BC). As we shall see, there is some strong new evidence for the middle part of that sequence, specifically for a subgroup of the middle group that is unified by the common inscription AN.

Part 1. New specimens and new countermarks²

a. Early group (c. 180-170 BC?)

7. KY|ZI in wreath in round punch. Obverse.

- a. 15.42 Side. ΔEI-NO. Paris M7603 ex Mowat coll. (ex Mme. Stamati Vinga). Mowat 1906, no. 2, pl. 10, 2. (*IGCH* 1721?).
- b. 16.67 Aspendos (Alexander type). Year 20 (194/3 BC). Price 2899. ANS 1951.35.53 ex Propontis 1950 hoard (*IGCH* 888). Waggoner 1979, 15 no. 93.
- c. 16.14 Perge (Alexander type). Year 32 (192/1 BC). Price 2946. Dionysos Ancient Coins & Antiquities, Ebay 372769355503, ending 26.ix.2019. **Plate 000, 1**
- d. 16.39 Side AP + thunderbolt. Bucephalus 15 (2023) 443. **Plate 000, 2.**

24. Tripod in rectangular frame. Obverse.

- a. 16.73 200-188 B.C. Sagalassos. Price 2985. ANS. 1953.120.1. Noe 1954, 88 pl. xiv. 11. Pl. 4, 24.
- b. 187-175 B.C. Seleucus IV, mint of Tarsus. SC 1309. Larissa 1968 (*IGCH* 237) no. 1083.
- c. 15.91 Aspendos Yr. 24 (190/89 B.C.). Price 2903. BM 2903d.
- d. 16.33 Side. ΔEI. Nomos obolos web 20 (2021) 814. Kunker elive 66 (2021) 149. **Plate 000, 3**

26. Head of Ammon in rectangular frame. Obverse.

- a. 15.95 Smyrna (Alexander type), Price 2247-58. c. 220-200 BC. Leu web 11 (2020) 695. **Plate 000, 4**

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² Numbering of the countermarks follows that of Meadows (2018). New countermarks are inserted where appropriate in the sequence. All new specimens are illustrated on **Plates 000-000**. Only countermarks for which the evidence has changed are included here.

b. Middle group (c. 170-150 BC)

14. Lion seated r., paw raised in round punch. Obverse.

- a. 16.19 ΔHM. G&M 126 (2003) 1406. Also bears Cist. cmk. of Pergamum.
- b. 15.9 [Δ]HM. Çiğlık 1997 hoard (*CH* 10.304). Also bears an Anchor cmk.
- c. XPY. Reported by Leschhorn (2015), p. 371, table 3.
- d. 16.20 ΔH-M. Kunker elive 69 (2021) 42. Also bears Lyre + A-N cmk. (below 4p). **Plate 000, 5**

14.1 Forepart of leaping lion in round punch. Obverse

- a. 15.10 Temnos (Alexander). Price 1689. Naville 59 (2020) 136. **Plate 000, 6**

15.1. Owl standing on Amphora; behind, palm branch, in round punch. Obverse

- a. 16.28 KAE-YX. Ancient and Medieval Coins Canada 3 (2021) 38. **Plate 000, 7**

c. The A-N Group

4. Lyre; to l. and r., A-N in round punch. Obverse.

- a. 16.37 XPY. CNG MB 66 (2004), 517. Kunker 402 (2024) 385. Unknown Findspot 2004 (*CH*-).
- b. 16.49 ΔH. CNG electronic 88 (2004) 60 (ex Lakeview, UBS 59 (2004), lot 5842).
- c. 16.12 XPY. UBS 59 (Lakeview, 2004), lot 5840. Also bears Bee cmk (see below, no. 000)
- d. 16.60 ΔH [M]. BM. *BMC* 29, ex Millingen coll., probably ex. Latour-Maubourg coll. (whence, Mionnet *Suppl.* vii, p. 63). Mowat (1906) nos. 59-60, pl. 10, 17. Also bears cist. cmk. of Adramytteion.
- e. 16.00 ΔH. BM. *BMC* 29A (p. 293) ex Sotheby 7.xii.1896 (Bunbury ii), lot 357. Mowat (1906) no. 30.
- f. 15.45 ΔH. BM. 1927.4.5.7. Also bears Bee cmk (see below, no. 12). Troxell (1982), pl. 1. J.
- g. 16.48 ΔH. Helsinki. *SNG Keckman* 678
- h. 16.41 ΔH. Copenhagen. *SNG Cop.* 395 (Lambros, 1898). Also bears Anchor cmk.
- i. 15.98 XPY. Paris 1966.467. *SNG Paris* 702. Also bears cist. cmk. of uncertain city.
- j. 16.06 XPY. Paris 1973.1.461. *SNG Paris* 706.
- k. Side Museum, on display, January 2017.
- l. KA-EY. Reported by Leschhorn (2015), p. 371, table 3.
- m. 15.48 ΔH. Gorny & Mosch Online Auction 259 (2018) 3346. Also bears Anchor cmk. **Plate 000, 8**
- o. 16.05 ΔH. Auktionen Münzhandlung Sonntag **30** (2019) 18. **Plate 000, 9**
- n. 16.04 XPY. Kunker elive 66 (2021) 148 16.04g Also bears cist. cmk. of Sardis. **Plate 000, 10**
- o. 16.20 ΔH. Kunker elive 67 (2021) 153. Also bears Anchor cmk. **Plate 000, 11**
- p. 16.20 ΔH-M. Kunker elive 69 (2021) 42. Also bears Lion cmk. (above 14d). **Plate 000, 12**

5.1 Head of Zeus; to l. and r., A-N in round punch. Obverse.

- a. 16.03. Temnos (Alexander type) Price 1680. Demetrius I hoard (*CH* 10.301), no. 180. **Plate 000, 13**
- b. 16.51 Temnos (Alexander type) Price 1680. Lanz Ebay 30352136, ending 9.4.2020. **Plate 000, 14**

5.2 Bucranium to l. and r., A-N in round punch. Obverse.

- a. 16.05 Side ΔH. Vcoins Marc Breitsprecher 39697. Also bears cist. cmk of Apameia. **Plate 000, 15**

5.3 Zebu forepart; above, AN in round punch. Obverse.

- a. 15.34 Miletus (Alexander type) Cf. Price 2198–2222A. CNG e-sale 537 (2023) 95. **Plate 000, 16**

d. Late Group (post c. 150 BC)

12. Bee in round punch. Obverse.

Tetradrachms

- a. 16.20 ΔH. UBS 59 ([Lakeview, 2004](#)), 5839. Also bears Cist. cmk. of Pergamum.
b. 16.12 XPY. UBS 59 ([Lakeview, 2004](#)), 5840. Bee is from same stamp as 12e. Also bears Lyre and A-N cmk.
c. 16.15 ΔEI. CNG electronic 86 (2004), 38. Unknown Findspot 2004 (CH-).
d. 16.47 XPY. Obolos 6 (2016) 563. Also bears Cist. cmk. of Apameia and Tripod + AII cmk. (see above, no. 10b)
e. 16.52 XPY. ANS 1953.171.929 (Holzer coll.). Bee is from same stamp as 12b. Also bears Cist. cmk. of Apameia.
f. 16.14 ΔEI. ANS 1953.171.927 (Holzer coll.). Also bears Cist. cmk. of Apameia.
g. 16.20 XPY. Berlin. Imhoof (1901-2), ii, p. 335, no. 8, pl. xi, 17. Mowat (1906) pp. 196 and 204, no. 56, pl. 10, 14. Also bears Cist. cmk. of Laodiceia.
h. ΔH. Klagenfurt 3016. Mowat (1906) no. 58, pl. 10, 16. Also bears Cist. cmk. of Sardis, clearly overstruck by the bee.
i. 15.60 ΔEI. Paris R2129. *SNG Paris* 672. Also bears Anchor cmk.
j. Illegible. Alexandria 1897 hoard (*IGCH* 1721). Dutihl (1898), p. 151. Mowat (1906) pp. 197 and 204, no. 57. Also bears Cist. cmk. of Pergamum
k. ΔIOΔ. Reported by Leschhorn (2015), p. 371, table 3.
l. CT. Reported by Leschhorn (2015), p. 371, table 3.
nn. 16.14 ΔEI. Naumann 114 (2022) 456. Also bears Cist. cmk. of Tralles. **Plate 000, 17**

22.1 Draped helmeted male bust right; behind, KI in oval punch.

- a. 3.84 Chios, drachm of ANΔPΩNAE, Lagos Reduced Attic Group C, c. 170-160 BC. Naumann 59 (2017) 123. **Plate 000, 18**
b. 3.91 Magnesia (Alexander drachm) Price 2009, mid 3rd century. Savoca Blue 139 (2022), 58. **Plate 000, 19**

Part 2. Commentary

a. Early group.

Three new specimens are now recorded for countermarks 7 and 24 (7c, 7d and 24d). All the host coins of these new marks exhibit some wear, although the issue of Side 7d, does appear relatively fresh. The early date range for this group seems thus still to hold. The new countermark which appears to depict a head of Zeus Ammon is the stand-out addition here.

The host coin of this countermark was produced, most probably, within the last two decades of the third century. It has seen some wear, but so too, apparently, has the countermark. A date of application within the period c. 180-170 BC may be possible, and so it is tentatively assigned here to the ‘early group’. As for the attribution, there are in fact, very few candidates iconographically for such a design. The island of Tenos aside, Mytilene is the mint that springs most immediately to mind as clearly associated with the type (Fig. 1a and 1b).³

Fig. 1a. Countermark 26a (detail)

Fig. 1b. Bronze coin of Mytilene (obv.) Paris FG 234

b. Middle group

14. Lion seated r. in round punch.

In 2018, I noted: ‘The lion countermark on coin 14b seems to have been overstruck on an anchor countermark. In any case, it appears fresher than the anchor, which seems to suggest that it was applied after the 170s BC. By contrast the countermark on coin 14a appears somewhat flattened when compared with the cistophoric countermark on the same coin. Conceivably this the result of damage to the countermark punch, or sudden blow to the lion countermark once it had been applied to this coin.’ The new specimen (d) also has a rather worn or flattened looking lion countermark, compared to a fresher looking lyre AN countermark. This serves to reinforce the relative sequence that I proposed in 2018, which sees this part of the middle group predating the A-N group.

14.1 Forepart of leaping lion in round punch.

The chronology of the Alexanders of Temnos, as revised by Cathy Lorber, suggests that the host coin of this new countermark had been struck before 162 BC.⁴ This specimen seems relatively fresh, so a date within the period c. 170-150 BC for this countermark may be proposed. Stylistically and iconographically, the lion forepart seems to find its closest parallel at Sardis (Fig. 2a and 2b).⁵

³ For the gold, see Bodenstedt (1981), series 4.67 and 5.104; silver, Babelon (1898) no. 1393; bronze, *BMC* 106-138.

⁴ Lorber (2010), p. 154.

⁵ Hochard (2020) Sardis 4.8.1827.

Fig. 2a. Countermark 14.1a

Fig. 2b. Bronze coin of Sardis (rev). Paris FG 1142.

15.1. Owl standing on Amphora; behind, palm branch, in round punch.

This new countermark is remarkable in a couple of respects. While occurrence of countermarks on issues of Side is, obviously, extremely common, their appearance on issues of the magistrate ΚΑΕΥΧ is extremely rare. Only six other instances are known to me: an example of the lyre + A-N countermark recorded by Wolfgang Leschhorn, four examples of bee countermarks on drachms, and one example of a facing head countermark, also on a drachm.⁶ There are, broadly speaking, two possible reasons for the comparative rarity of issues of ΚΑΕΥΧ bearing countermarks. If the countermarking episode was contemporary with the production of the host coins, then this would suggest that the majority of the countermarks were applied before the ΚΑΕΥΧ issues had fully entered circulation. At first glance, this explanation might seem to be supported by the fact that we can state on the basis of other evidence that the issues of ΚΑΕΥΧ were the last to be produced. However, this explanation can almost certainly be ruled out, since there are strong grounds to think that some at least of these countermarks were applied after the coinage of Side had ceased to be produced. The alternative explanation would be that fewer coins of ΚΑΕΥΧ entered the circulation pool in which the countermarks were applied. It is tempting to suggest that this difference in circulation may be connected to the different agency that lies behind the earlier Sidetan issues, which for the most belong to the period of Seleucid control of the city, and the issues of ΚΑΕΥΧ which were struck most probably between c. 183 and 175 BC.⁷

Fig. 3a Countermark 15.1

Fig. 3b. Priene (rev.), Paris Y 20243. Fonds général 2073

Fig. 3c. Synnada (rev.), British Museum 1920.5.16.92

⁶ Meadows (2018) 4l, 12o, 12ee, 12ff, 12mm and 16b.

⁷ For the chronology see Meadows (2006), p. 157. In this respect, the countermarks partially resemble to behaviour of the cistophoric countermarks, which have also found abundantly on the earlier issues of Side, but never on those of ΚΑΕΥΧ. This may provide support to the notion that the earlier Sidetan issues formed part of the Seleucid indemnity payment.

As to the attribution of this new countermark, two obvious candidates present themselves. On the one hand there is Priene, already attested as a countermarking state,⁸ which issued bronzes in the second century BC bearing precisely the design of an owl on an amphora. Equally, there is Synnada, which issued contemporary bronzes of an identical type (see Fig. 3a, b and c). On the current state of the evidence, it seems impossible to choose firmly between the two cities. The fact that Priene is already attested with a countermark that leaves no doubt as to its identity, may offer some reason to favour the claim of Synnada. On the other hand, as the map below shows, Synnada is some way to the east of the other cities that can be firmly identified as countermarking authorities.

c. The AN group

In 2018, I gathered within my ‘middle group’ a series of five countermarks that all bore the letters A and N (1-5: Eagle, fulmen, radiate head, lyre and tripod(?)). Given the wide iconographic range of the countermarks, I rejected (pp. 197-8) previous attempts to read these characters as the initial letters of a mint, and suggested instead that the letters might stand for Ἀττικὸν or Ἀλεξανδρεῖον Νόμισμα (Attic or Alexandrine coinage), with the countermarks serving to reassert the value of this now rather worn circulation pool in a world where the cistophorus had also come to serve as an important part of the coin supply. In the intervening six years, no fewer than three more such countermarks have come to light (5.1-5.3: Head of Zeus, Bucranium and Zebu forepart). Any lingering desire to see these letters as the initials of a minting city must surely now be extinguished.

The attribution of the three new types to mints or cities is, as with the five already known, not straightforward. The head of Zeus is an extremely common design on many bronze coinages of Asia Minor. Stylistically, we can find fairly good parallels at Tralles or Antioch on the Maeander, for example (see Fig. 4a and 4b), but no one solution imposes itself.

Fig. 4a. Countermark 5.1a and b

Fig. 4b. Bronze coin of Tralles (obv). Naumann 52 (2017) 1327.

For the forepart of zebu, both Antioch and Kibyra are obvious possibilities, since two other countermarks with this design can clearly be attributed to these two cities (see below on countermarks 6 and 11). But Tralles, too, could be a candidate for this design.⁹

As for the chronology of this phenomenon, I suggested in 2018 a *terminus post quem* of c. 170 BC on the basis of the relative sequence of a radiate head + AN countermark and an anchor countermark on the same coin (pp. 201 and 204, no. 3a). But I could not then rule out a connection with the Zebu forepart + AN + ΠΑ + ΣΩ countermark (no. 6) which clearly belongs

⁸ Meadows (2028) no. 8 (ΠΙΠΗ + Δ).

⁹ On the zebu at Tralles see Meadows (2014).

after 144/3 BC. New evidence, combined with a crucial piece that I had missed, suggests that a much firmer and more precise date can now be offered for this phenomenon, and that these countermarks can indeed be dissociated from countermark 6.

The crucial new piece of evidence consists of countermark 5.1. In April 2020, the auction house Lanz Numismatik offered for sale an Alexander tetradrachm of Temnos bearing a countermark of a bearded head with long hair, presumably to be identified as Zeus. To either side are the letters A-N. In fact, this countermark was already known, having been published by Cathy Lorber in her catalogue of the Demetrius I hoard (*CH* 10.301), on coin no. 180, also an Alexander of Temnos, illustrated on her plate 38. These two new countermarks are in fact struck on the same issue (Price 1680), signed apparently by two magistrates, one using a monogram made of the letters A, E and Y, the other with one formed of the letter Σ, Y and P (Æ and Ξ). Versions of these monograms in fact appear on another ‘variety’ identified by Price under the number 1679: Æ and Ξ.

Since the appearance of Price’s corpus, the chronology of the Alexanders of Temnos has become a lot clearer, thanks to Lorber’s publication of the Demetrius I hoard (*CH* 10.301). There she points out the fact that type 1679 was present in the Ma’ Aret en Numan hoard (*CH* 6.37; 7.98; 8.433; 9.511), and that this issue must, therefore, predate the deposit of that hoard in c. 162 BC. In fact, the specimen illustrated by Mattingly in his publication of that hoard is in virtually uncirculated state, suggesting that it had been struck not long before its deposit. Since Price 1680 is simply a minor variety of the same magistrates, it seems clear that it too must date shortly before 162 BC.¹⁰

Although, given the parlous nature of our evidence, we cannot push too far the coincidence of both countermarks being struck on the same issue, we can state with some degree of certainty that they were applied perhaps not too long after the production of Price 1680, since we now know that one countermarked coin was deposited in the Demetrius I hoard, for which a burial date of 151 BC seems quite secure. Our countermarks thus seem to have been applied perhaps in the period c. 165-151 BC. We can thus confirm that they must be dissociated from countermark 6 (Zebu forepart + AN + ΠΑ + ΣΩ), which cannot have been applied before 144/3 BC (see further below, part d).

d. The Late group

22.1 Draped helmeted male bust right; behind, KI in oval punch.

The new countermark featuring a draped male bust wearing a helmet, accompanied by the letters KI must surely be attributed to Kibyra. The design precisely matches that of the obverse of the second-century silver coinage of this city (cf. Fig. 5a and 5b), and the initial letters of the city’s name confirm it.

¹⁰ See Lorber (2010), p. 154. It is not clear on what ground she proposes the separation of these two issues in her table on p. 154.

Fig. 5 a. Detail of coin 22.1 b

Fig. 5b. Detail of drachm of Kibyra, Paris, BnF 1972.1340.43

One cannot but be reminded of countermark 22, with the rider that similarly matches the reverse of the same coinage. The host coins offer some possibility of establishing a date of this new countermark. Coin 22.1a, a heavily worn Alexander drachm of Magnesia, is of very limited value. Coin 22.1b is more suggestive, originally struck sometime shortly after 170 BC, it had seen some wear before being countermarked. Interestingly, the host coin of countermark 22 was also struck in the 160s, and we might consider the possibility that the two countermarks were contemporary. I tentatively suggested a date for countermark 22 of 142/1 BC, on the basis of the era-date it may bear.¹¹

We should also briefly reconsider here the case of countermark 11, a butting zebu, also with the letters KI. An attribution to Kibyra seems similarly certain, as has been noted in the past. In 2018 I placed this with hesitation in the middle group of countermarks, but there is no strong reason why it should not belong in the late group with the other Kibyran marks.

Finally, we may return to countermark **6. Zebu forepart + AN + ΠΑ + ΣΩ in a round punch**, which is attested by two specimens:

- a. 16.37 Side ΔΗ. CNG e-sale 364 (2015) 297 (ex Witschonke). Also bears Cist. cmk. Of Sardis. **Fig. 6a.**
- b. 16.29 Athens. Thompson, *New Style* 1846. (144/3 BC). ANS 1944.100.85073.

The hard *terminus post quem* of 144/3 for this countermark is given by the host coin of specimen b. While no new examples of this countermarked have emerged, we may be able to make an advance in attribution thanks to another new piece of evidence. Peter Thonemann has drawn my attention to a new example of the silver tetradrachm coinage of Antioch on the Maeander, with a zebu reverse, that is signed by a ΠΑΠΙΑΣ and a ΣΩΧΑΡΗΣ (Fig. 6b).

¹¹ Meadows (2018), p. 212. However, it cannot now be entirely ruled out that the legend is a blundered version of the KI that appears on countermark 22.1.

Countermark 6a.

*Fig. 6b. Silver tetradrachm of Antioch on the Maeander.
Roma 29 (2023) 198.*

The coincidence of types and names with the ΠΑ and ΣΩ of the countermark is remarkable, and strongly confirms that this countermark should be assigned to Antioch, as I suggested (p. 205) in 2018. It may well be, in fact, that the AN that appears on this countermark represents the first two letters of ANTIOXEON. As we have seen, in the light of the new evidence discussed above (part c) for the chronology of the AN group, it seems that this countermark must be detached from them.

In his study of the silver of Antioch, Thonemann (2019) has convincingly argued for a first century date for the main body of the coinage. However, the new coin is somewhat different from his Group A with which it ostensibly shares types. The style of the head of Apollo on the obverse is very different and appears to be accompanied by a small depiction of a boot at the back. The reverse, in contrast to the rest of the silver of the city, provides an ethnic in full: not just ANTIOXEON, but ANTIOXEON TON IPOΣ TOI MAIANΔPOI. And where the rest of the silver is signed by one magistrate, the new coin is signed by two. There may be some reason to suggest, therefore, that this coin is earlier than the main run of coinage and belongs in the latter half of the 2nd century rather than the 1st.¹²

Conclusions

¹² We might also note that the weight of this new specimen at 16.26g, is at the heavy end of the range encompassed by the 1st-century coinage: see Thonemann (2019), pp. 66-7.

Map of certain and possible sites of countermarking

While much remains uncertain, the addition of new evidence begins to flesh out the possible geographical extent of the second century countermarking phenomenon (Map). In general, it seems to fall both within the footprint of the Attalid kingdom, but also to include a number of cities that were demonstrably left free after the Peace of Apameia. Moreover, if the identification of countermarks applied at Myndos and Halicarnassus were to prove correct, then it seems that the phenomenon may have extended into the freed region of Caria.

The chronology of some of this phenomenon has become a little clearer too. The ‘Middle’ group, including those countermarks marked with the letters A-N seems now to belong squarely between the early 160s BC and c. 151 BC. That is to say their application almost certainly coincides with the start of the cistophoric coinage in the early 160s.¹³ Furthermore, the presence of a small number of countermarks on the ΚΑΕΥΧ issues of Side, on which the cistophoric countermarks are never found, demonstrates that this phase of countermarking postdates the cistophoric countermarking. As a working hypothesis we may thus suggest that these later countermarks were applied by civic authorities to validate Attic weight coins in a world where the cistophorus had become a favoured means of payment on the part the Attalid royal authorities. On such a hypothesis it becomes attractive to interpret the letters AN that characterise a significant number of these countermarks as standing for Ἀττικὸν or Ἀλεξάνδρειον Νόμισμα (Attic or Alexandrine coin).

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¹³ For this date for the beginning of cistophoric coinage see most recently Meadows (2020).

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